

Wikipedia-based hybrid-search RAG with prompt decomposition for MedHopQA

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Abstract

While Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) mitigates hallucinations in Large Language Models (LLMs), its performance degrades for queries requiring multi-hop reasoning due to semantic retrieval limitations and context poisoning. We propose an enhanced RAG framework combining hybrid search (keyword + semantic retrieval), reciprocal rank fusion, and optimized prompt decomposition. Evaluated on the MedHopQA benchmark, our system achieves a 0.53 Exact-Match (EM) and 0.59 Concept Level scores for short answers, leveraging a curated knowledge base of 225k health-related Wikipedia articles. All experiments were conducted using Python 3.10 with local inference via Ollama serving the `thewindmom/llama3-med42-8b` model. Further improvements are possible through refined prompt engineering and retrieval parameter tuning.

Keywords

Retrieval-Augmented Generation, Large Language Models, Multi-hop Reasoning, Biomedical QA

1. Introduction

Large Language Models (LLMs) are prone to generating factually incorrect or nonsensical outputs—a phenomenon known as "hallucination" [1]. Such errors are particularly problematic in biomedical domains, where inaccuracies can directly impact decision-making. Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) partially addresses this by grounding LLMs in external knowledge sources [2], but standard implementations struggle with complex queries requiring multi-hop reasoning (i.e., inferring connections across documents) due to two key limitations:

- **Semantic retrieval brittleness:** Dense vector search often retrieves superficially relevant but factually inadequate passages.
- **Context poisoning:** Noisy or biased source documents degrade output quality, especially when synthesizing information from multiple retrievals.

To overcome the main challenge of MedHopQA task, our approach (visualized in Figure 1) utilizes: (1) hybrid search (keyword + semantic retrieval) and reciprocal rank fusion to improve recall, and (2) prompt decomposition techniques to guide multi-step reasoning.

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Figure 1: Architecture of our enhanced RAG framework. Dotted lines represent LLM-driven steps. Solid lines denote retrieval and ranking processes.

2. Methods

2.1. Implementation Details

All pipeline components were implemented in Python 3.10, with LLM inference handled locally through Ollama serving the thewindmom/llama3-med42-8b model [3], which is a fine-tuning of

llama3. This configuration provided optimal balance between biomedical knowledge retention and computational efficiency on our hardware. For RAG-system inference, we used a single NVIDIA GeForce RTX 5080 GPU and 11th Gen Intel i7-11700 (16) CPU on a local machine.

2.2. Information Source

The MedHopQA test set comprises questions addressing specialized biomedical domains, including rare diseases, pharmacologic agents, genetic markers, therapeutic interventions, medical journals and niche medical history (e.g., "*Which London suburb housed the pioneering institutions that influenced John Langdon Down's work at Earlswood Asylum?*"). The test set contained 10k questions and the evaluation of metrics is done on 1k questions, hidden from contestants. Given that these questions were derived from publicly available Wikipedia content, we selected Wikipedia as our primary text corpus. This decision was motivated by the hypothesis that answer accuracy could be optimized when both questions and answers originate from the same source material.

We downloaded Wikipedia dump *pages-articles-multistream.xml.bz2*, which contained current revisions only, no talk or user pages. We extracted more than 225k health-related articles, including article stubs, from the compressed dump based on Wikipedia category matching, which are listed below every Wikipedia article and then stored it in a JSONL file. To find the relevant categories, we used PETSscan [4], thus, retrieving more than 100k relevant categories. Each article text in JSONL also has associated metadata (article title and url, listed categories and extracted links), which can be used to enhance the retrieval quality in RAG pipelines.

2.3. Document Splitting (Chunking)

One of the most crucial aspects of RAG is document splitting, as an inadequate splitting strategy can lead to poorer retrieval accuracy. While there are many approaches to document splitting for RAG (such as semantic splitting [5]), we opted for a more conservative method—recursive character text splitting. The chunk size is set to 512 characters, with a chunk overlap of 32 for both stores. As suggested in some studies, an overlap of 10–20% of the chunk size helps maintain continuity and context between chunks [6].

2.4. Stores and Retrievers

We used Langchain ChromaDB [7] [8] integration in Python3.10 to create vector store from document chunks, utilizing MedEmbed-small-v0.1 [9] embedding model. The distance metric in the vector store is cosine similarity, which is scale-invariant.

For keyword-based search, we used the BM25S algorithm [10]. The store which contains all of the text fragments from Wikipedia, is fully local.

2.5. Hybrid Search (Ensemble Retrieval)

Instead of choosing a single store for retrieval step, we used Langchain ensemble retrieval, which is a combination of both approaches, and assigned weights for each retriever: 0.6 for semantic search and 0.4 for keyword search. These weights were chosen heuristically while following examples provided in Langchain documentation. Each component retrieves 5 most relevant document chunks for each query and then reranks them using Reciprocal Rank Fusion (RRF) algorithm based on the assigned weights [11]. After reranking, the LLM receives top-5 most relevant documents.

2.6. Prompt Engineering and Optimization

Our pipeline employs structured prompting across three stages, each requiring a separate LLM call using thewindmom/llama3-med42-8b via Ollama [12]:

1. Query Decomposition

Objective: Break multi-hop questions into simpler, retrievable sub-questions.

Break down this medical question into simple, factual sub-questions that can be answered independently from medical literature. Each sub-question should:

1. Be answerable with a specific fact or short answer
 2. Build logically toward answering the main question
 3. Use clear medical terminology.
 4. Duplicate the initial question in the numbered list of sub-questions
 5. Don't make the questions redundant
 6. Always make no more than 4 subquestions
 7. Don't lose context
 8. NEVER make the sub-questions more complex than the initial question
- Output ONLY the sub-questions as a numbered list, nothing else.

2. Query Optimization

Objective: Make the queries optimized for retrieval.

You are a medical question optimizer. Optimize this specific medical sub-question for document retrieval but never answer them (e.g. "Which medical specialty is likely involved in the diagnosis and treatment of angioliipomas?" is not "Dermatology involvement in angioliipoma diagnosis and management" but "Angioliipoma medical specialty") Focus only on the specific aspect asked about. Don't incorporate the main question. NEVER lose context (e.g. "Which medical subspecialty primarily focuses on the diagnosis and management of skin lesions?" is not "Dermatology" but "Dermatology skin lesions medical specialty")

3. Subquestion answers

Objective: Create intermediate answers optimized for retrieval.

You are an expert in medicine, molecular biology and biochemistry. Answer the question below based strictly on the context above and using common sense. If the answer cannot be found in the context, say "I couldn't find a definitive answer in my sources."

4. Answer Fusion

Objective: Aggregate sub-question answers into a final response.

Combine these answers to sub-questions into a coherent final answer. Be precise and cite sources when available. Use [1], [2], etc. notation to cite wikipedia pages.

Sub-question Answers: {intermediate_answers}

Source References: {source_references}

Original question: {main_question}

ALWAYS Extract a concise SINGLE and SHORT final answer (1-3 word long) following these rules:

1. Use complete formal names (e.g., "Diabetes Mellitus, type 2")
2. For chromosome questions: format as "Chromosome X"
3. For syndromes named after people: use full name (e.g., "Carpenter's syndrome")
4. For yes/no: answer only "Yes" or "No"
5. For true/false: answer only "TRUE" or "FALSE"
6. Pick a single answer without writing synonyms
7. Don't overthink or overengineer the answers
8. Make sure the answers are not recursive
9. For drug questions: don't mention drug form
10. If unknown, write "N/A" and nothing else

After a short answer, write your explanation and cite wikipedia article web pages.

3. Results

Our enhanced RAG framework demonstrated moderate performance on biomedical question answering, as shown in Table 1. The system achieved a average concept-level score of 0.591 and an improved exact match (EM) score of 0.526, with median values of 0.659 and 0.549, respectively. Due to time constraints, we were unable to conduct ablation studies comparing basic RAG with hybrid RAG or Decomposition RAG with non-Decomposition RAG. These comparisons will be addressed in future work.

Table 1

Performance metrics of our RAG system

Metrics	Concept Level Score	Exact Match (EM)
Average	0.591	0.526
Median	0.659	0.549

Performance remains sub-optimal for certain complex queries. Future directions include investigating few-shot prompting strategies and optimizing retrieval parameters to enhance accuracy.

4. Online Resources

The code for this project is available at [GitHub](#)

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